

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Please initial each box

As part of this research study, I agree to participate in the Resilience Training Programme (RTP) intervention and one of two focus group discussions. I confirm that I have read and understand the Participant Information Sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

I understand that taking part in this qualitative part of the study will involve a reflective focus group discussions about my experience of the training programme.

I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I am free to withdraw at any time up until the point the data are analysed on the 15th of May 2025, without giving a reason, and that I do not have to answer any questions I am not comfortable with.

I understand that the information I provide will be used for a postgraduate dissertation and may form part of a published article and/or conference/seminar paper.

I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me will not be shared beyond the study team. I also agree to keep the discussion in the focus group confidential

I agree that my anonymised information can be quoted in research outputs.

I give permission for the data collected and transcribed during my reflective discussions by the audio recording that I provide to be used for future research and learning.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Researcher

Date

Signature

One copy to be kept by the participant, one to be kept by the researcher

Experts of the original coded reflective focus group discussions transcripts

I unlocked many things in myself, gained awareness about many things.

It was my first time in taking a training. I thought it will be good to try it. Then I felt very comfortable, I was waiting for the next session. I like it, that's why I maintained attending. I thought it will be annoying, but was surprised it's engaging and motivating. At ease, with great atmosphere, ever a dull moment; I was interested a lot. I thought it will be a heavy activity, but it wasn't.

I was curious to know about RTP but didn't had expectations.

I wanted to learn the competences and tools to use them in my personal and professional life, and in case I face challenges.

relationships.

I expected it to be good for me. I wanted to find out more about myself.

I expected it to be good for me to learn how to understand myself.

First impressions

A little bit bizarre in the good sense, the wheel of life satisfaction, never thought about this, surprising, my qualities, my life satisfaction, I never thought I can adjust the use of my character strengths in contexts, but it was surprising for me how I can enhance or diminish uses of my strengths

I wasn't surprised because I works on myself in my mind.

For me, it pushed me to think, to think about myself, my strengths, never thought about my strengths. The

seemed very easy with COPOPT, which I didn't expect, and I was thinking if we will really attain our goal at the end of the training. It was all new for all the participants. All new, new, new everything new, we liked the COPOPT and how it helped putting us in the flow of the training. New discovery, everything was new, all the activities.

The program is original and new, well-structured and organised from the beginning.

We learnt a lot of new things from the most first workshop.

It made me think about how to act when something goes wrong or when I feel challenged and stressed to better manage them.

I learned how to manage our emotions and learnt our 5 top character strengths.

I was surprised that the training (RTP-COPOPT) was fun and original.

Surprised from the beginning because it's very new especially in Tunisia, how it confirmed things I already know about myself in clear manner, I learned deep things about myself I never knew about them, and also, I was faced with the challenge to choose only 5-character strengths from all the 24

Choosing the 5 top character strengths was challenging but very interesting and enjoyable; The fact to be in a situation to choose 5 from the 24 was difficult, serious but very enjoyable.

liked it.

I thought it will be annoying , very dull, that I will be fed up, and that will force myself to attend and commit to the training without really being motivated to do that , but I was surprised that it was awesome and that I wanted to come and awaited the sessions. It helped me know myself, I'm learning about myself. I laughed and cried, issues that I forgot, ignored, and they came back with the visualisation technique, and I learned a lot about myself, without the resistance I had before.

I thought I forgot things in my life, and with the visualisation technique I recall all these memories, I cried. Things that I tried and thought I've succeeded in

and how I act in life; The awareness in itself helped me understand myself better.

I discovered that some of my top character strengths weren't helping me, and I learned to balance my life in accordance to this and use them in a more balanced way to give myself my rights in my life.

I'm learning about myself, the good and the bad, it's a process, so I accepted to follow the training path without sorrow, but only to reconcile with myself. I was learning about myself, I wanted to know more about myself each time, intrigued about what else I can know in the upcoming workshops. I learned good things and bad things. I revised my interactions with others, learned

I felt my real me, I felt comfortable, I realised that this is what can make me change to the best.

I felt at ease and open with myself.

I felt proud of myself because I found that I am near all the positive psychology principles and outcomes about wellbeing, positive education and resilience.

I felt relaxed, peaceful, when you know how you think from deep, deep inside, when you know what your strengths are, I felt involved and moving in the right direction.

I felt interested by the interventions, and motivated to change things in myself, and I felt more confident.

I felt heard by

others, free to act, write and describe about myself without judgements, I felt the freedom to express myself without judgment, especially that no one sees my notes and we are in the training without obstacles.

I felt skilled after all the activities, games, trainings, I felt prepared, ready and more skilled and qualified in the subsequent workshops in reflecting and answering questions, especially in co-coaching with my peer, I liked it and enjoyed it a lot.

I started in changing my behaviour and reflect consciously on how I think, focusing on more positive way of thinking and try to challenge negative thinking, consciously think

about how I think, I gained an inside understanding of myself, calm and mindful.

I understood better myself, felt a little bit stronger, calm, less stressed, more positive, try to be calm and less stressed and try to change myself.

Challenges or difficulties encountered when using RTP-COPOPT

The visualisation technique took me an effort to imagine the miracle question. Choosing 6-character strengths from the 24, and Appreciative inquiry was challenging (drawing was difficult, how to make it concrete on paper was difficult (3 participants)).

The COPOPT is meant to guide me in understanding what are the good things in myself

participants)

Same thing as my peer said, in plus, the paper is heavy for your mind to use and annoying because of how it is presented.

The game really captivated me, I was very involved.

9/10

I wished I was excellent in english. The cards were helping, the colours, the design, very beautiful, motivated me in engaging with the training through using the game.

The game is general, we can all have 6-character strengths, anyone can do them, and the resilience training was more focused on our behaviours, beliefs, much more serious.

The game simplified concepts and techniques of

the activities.
 Maybe if it wasn't in a game, I will not do it and commit as I did with a gamified training. COPOPT kept me engaged with the whole RTP.

The game (COPOPT) is more friendly, easier, light, interesting, very helpful especially that it was at the beginning of the training, it kept us interested, with it it's easier to grasp the concepts and understand very easily and quickly the concepts.

If there wasn't COPOPT, we would run away from the training. The cards were useful, helped avoided feeling bored, and made us feeling motivated. The other paper-based activities were also helpful, while COPOPT was even much better. }

repeated by 3 participants).

The PPIs helped me practice gratitude, I felt PP COPOPT helped practically apply the activities of Positive Psychology.

Overall experience of the RTP-COPOPT programme: Useful and not useful aspects of RTP-COPOPT and reasons

The sequence and the content are perfect, even if optional activities like "flow, passion, and meaning in life" were challenging as concepts.

I think you should explain the meaning of the pictures in self-compassion after we finished the session, I wanted to know why I choose this picture and not the other picture just after the session and maybe talk about it a little bit.

In the very last activity, the appreciative inquiry

..Repetition and discomfort with drawing in Appreciative Inquiry

- ..Suggestion for Artificial Intelligence enhanced tools in Apprecia
- .. Suggestion for tech-enhanced visual expression (Artificial Intelli
- ..Suggestion for Tech-mediated visual expression

- ..Conceptual challenges with abstract/existential PP t
- ..Perceived developmental limitation on purpose exp
- ..Self-awareness
- ..Conceptual challenges with abstract/existential PP t

..Value of character strengths and strengths wheel effectiveness

, we didn't like drawing because we're not good at it and because we already wrote a lot about it , so we already had it written, so maybe we could have tablets to help us draw more representative pictures about our ideas , and, maybe use artificial intelligence to help us generate them, because the drawing wasn't pertinent. (3 participants repeated the same thing)

I found that I don't have the capacity to think about purpose. Thinking about purpose, meaning was difficult, maybe early for my age.

Parts and aspects of RTP-COPOPT particularly useful and reasons

Character strengths and strengths wheel were the most useful. (4 participants)

reflecting about all that.

I learned what bothers me and begin to start fixing them, from the wheel of life and character strengths.

Character strengths cards because they are helpful in both personal and professional, taking notes was very helpful, and how we needed to reflect and write everything in our notebooks. (2 participants)

The part of the Best Possible Self visualization activity, because it gives you the possibility to think about how you want your life , and help make you do the steps to become like you want to be.

Finding your strengths allows

you to get to know your inner criteria.

About RTP- COOPT coaching style (added by the participants during discussions)

The most beautiful thing is that no one knows what we're writing. It's all confidential, and we can write whatever we want. (6 participants)

Benefits of RTP- COOPT

Yes, of course, there were lots of benefits. When you talk about yourself out loud and see it with your eyes or you write it and you were never used to face yourself make you aware about your deepest issues and you know that you'll return to these things and resolve them, you stop ignoring them and become aware of their presence and that you need to take actions.

Wellbeing is the main benefit we gained (7 participants).

I started applying

in diminishing the use of some character strengths that weren't helping me, this helped me a lot. Before I wasn't able to do that, I did not see the benefits of that action.

Genuinely enjoyable experience that helped know myself. I changed already things in myself, I felt amazingly comfortable, very peaceful, and very calm, contented, and mindful. When I practised, I felt relieved, I felt free, relieved, expressed myself even if it was all confidential and my notes were not seen by others. I felt free to write everything and all.

I was very engaged even if it was my only new training.

I started taking decisions to my own life and thinking about my

want to change yourself or not, all of it.

It's useful for getting a clear idea of yourself from a different angle. The benefits are having a clear idea of my priorities in life, the areas I care about and the character traits I want to develop.

Less or least useful part/aspects of RTP-COPOPT

The activity where we had to choose 3 domains to work on and then we had questions to answer, the questions were similar, it takes a lot of self concentration, the questions are demanding lots of reflection.

The emotional granularity wheel activity (2 participants)

The visualisation was normal because I used to imagine. (2 participants)

Unclear or difficult parts or concepts of RTP-COPOPT

The use of strengths wheel in contexts activity (2 participants)

I didn't find any part is less useful (5 participants)

The 3 domains of the wheel of life activity, we found the vocabulary was difficult for us.

I think because you trained us, it is easier, we think that because you trained us and explained everything. It seemed difficult but when applying them, they are easier than we thought. We think thanks to the coaching itself. (4 participants agreed about it)

One-to-one self-compassion, and the co-coaching were difficult.

Emotional granularity wheel

life.

I learned how to understand myself, my emotions and others, in how to manage the stress, in how to understand others, especially to understand others that also have their situations.

I knew with the visualisation technique that I have many situations that are bothering me unconsciously, and facing my situations with the self compassion without judgements, and when we tried to put our strengths in some contexts, they're not all helpful and weaken us, so now I understand that it's the same for others, and I can understand them better now.

I had anger and anxiety peaks

less frightening.

Changes noticed when approach challenges- impact on resilience

Impact on way of thinking about the challenges ahead

Impact on coping with/recovery from adversity

Impact on adapting to/coping with life's inevitable demands

It's more about my wellbeing, it's better, my feelings, my emotions more positive and persistent.

For the relationships I changed and now feel contented in how I balanced how I interact with others. Usually, I act and react on time if there is an issue with someone, but this time I just stayed quiet and feeling okay, less anger less automatic reaction.

I became conscious about how to balance my life emotionally and become more contented. Now I don't care, become more mindful, don't react automatically, but think before and can choose not to interact in a negative way. Now

especially during the exams, now I see the obstacles as opportunities to learning.

I felt myself more motivated than before in managing my time for the revision for the exams, I felt more capable of managing my time in my exam period, managing my emotions, in preparing the exams.

I enjoyed taking my notes about my self reflections without anyone seeing them.

It helped me see myself deeper, move on, let the past and fix on the future, love myself, want to live my life happier and do what I want.

The RTP-COPOPT helped me know my priorities and knowing more about myself.

it.
 I learned emotion management, self-compassion, I enjoyed to be actively heard.
 Emotion management/ enjoyable experience, learned a lot of new things, learned about our top character strength/ I enjoyed the whole experience
 RTP helped me see myself, see what I want, what I love, so yes it helped me.

I gained the skill of how to talk to myself, how to listen to my needs, how to fix and organize my goals, how to deal with the problems and try to find a solution.

Each part of the RTP gave me the possibility to discover more about myself, to move deeply in

	<p>were younger, and remember the important things in our lives. Yes</p> <p>Yes, I would recommend the RTP-COPOPT to others, absolutely! (6 participants)</p> <p>Yes, I would recommend the RTP-COPOPT to others. (2 participants)</p>
Evaluation of the RTP-COPOPT	It's good as it is (12 participants)

Table 1. Original codes under Sub-theme- Expectations as motivators for theme 1-Sources of motivation and engagement

Codes under Sub-theme 1.1 (Expectations as motivators) of theme 1-Sources of motivation and engagement	Coded segment
- Clear psychological needs for resilience trainings (10 participants)	10
- Expected good to understand the self	1
- Expected good to understand the self (2 participants)	2
- Curiosity as motivation; Openness to learning (3 participants)	3
- Holistic wellbeing goals (mental, emotional, relational) (2 participants)	2
- Build stronger relationships.	1
- Expected better understand my emotions	1
- Emotional regulation expectation	1
- expected better Emotional agility in professional setting	1
- Better interactions and communications (2 participants)	2
- Seeking emotional regulation's tools	1
- Novelty of experience; Lack of prior exposure (5 participants)	5
- Active learning (PosEd) as a goal (2 participants)	2
- Fostering resilience as a goal	1
- Emotional intelligence goals	1
- Learning how to improve mental health as a goal	1
- Learning how to build strong relationships as a goal (2 participants)	2
- Learning how to enhance problem solving as a goal	1
- No prior expectations	1
- Learning how to improve emotional agility as a goal	1

Table 2. Original codes under Sub-theme - Impressions and experience with RTP as sources of sustained motivation & engagement (for theme 1-Sources of motivation and engagement)

Codes under Sub-theme- Impressions and experience with RTP as sources of sustained motivation & engagement of theme 1-Sources of motivation and engagement	Coded segment
- Understanding the inner self as a goal	1
- Deep engagement during RTP workshops	1
- Novelty vs familiarity in affecting interest and engagement (2 participants)	2
- High engagement despite unfamiliarity and novelty	1
- Sustained trust and confidentiality throughout the entire RTP's workshops (6 participants)	6
- Role of first session in retention via strengths' identification	1
- Motivation through insight via RTP	1
- Surprising engagement; Shift from boredom to motivation (2 participants)	2
- good surprises (3 participants)	3
- Application to professional relationships; Social-emotional learning	2
- Skill development goals; Transferable learning	1
- Self-evaluation; Alignment with life purpose	1
- Sustained engagement	1
- Positive learning experience	1
- Experience of ACR	1
- Novel approach	1
- Surprise at method	1
- Positive engagement	1
- flow	1
- Novelty and originality of RTP (3 participants)	3
- Pleasant surprise	1
- RTP's progression facilitates involvement	1
- Early engagement (2 participants)	2
- Positive emotional tone	1
- Engagement despite difficulty	1

- Engagement despite difficulty	1
- Preconception vs lived experience	1
- Unexpected joy and emotional investment	1
- Transformation into genuine engagement (2 participants)	2
- Surprise from cards' prompts	1
- surprise and novelty	1
- Surprise and novelty of both visualisation technique and miracle questions	1
- Surprise and novelty of PP tools	1
- Surprise about top personal character strengths	1
- Shift in motivation (2 participants)	2
- Joyful experience	1
- Practical value drove motivation and engagement	1
- Sustained motivation and engagement via surprising adapted and tailored PPIs	1
- Confidentiality promotes freedom and expression of thoughts and insights (6 participants)	6
- AC and ACR advantages in promoting motivation and engagement	1
- Psychological safety; Motivation to return (3 participants)	3
- Enjoyment of co-coaching activities	1

Table 3. Merged code categories within Theme 1- Sources of motivation and engagement.

Merged code category	n = Code category occurrences
Intrinsic expectations for personal development and psychological growth.	21
Expectations to better understand and regulate emotions in self and societal circumstances.	10
Expectations related to novelty and interesting ways of delivery (e.g., active learning, co-coaching).	9
Some participants' willingness to discover rather than to anticipate.	1
RTP's innovative components resulted in heightened levels of interest and emotional engagement.	22
The importance of ensuring a safe, trustworthy environment for the development of intrinsic motivation and engagement.	15
Experience that is marked by deep emotional immersion and ongoing involvement.	11
Intrinsic motivation via learning's practical relevance, self-awareness, and meaning.	8

socially interactive PPIs activities (e.g. ACR, co-coaching) created emotionally engaging entry points, stimulating initial and continued participation.	5
As RTP progresses, participants' perspectives change, and their level of interest and involvement rises.	3

Table 4. Original codes under Subtheme -Positive evaluation of anything related to the RTP for theme2- Evaluation of the experience and future recommendation

Codes under Subtheme-Positive evaluation of anything related to the RTP of theme2- Evaluation of the experience and future recommendation	Coded segment
- RTP good and rewarding (10 participants)	10
- Perceived coherence of RTP (11 participants)	11
- Endorsement of the RTP's organisation, presentation, and structure (11 participants)	11
- No parts of the RTP considered less useful (5 participants)	5
- Best Possible Self exercise enhances deep self-reflection	1
- Best Possible Self as impactful on self-determination	1
- Highly engaged with RTP	1
- Surprised by enhanced self-engagement during RTP	1
- Appreciation of the part of RTP	1
- Great experience	1
- Appropriateness of timing (4 participants)	4
- Perceived timeliness (7 participants)	7
- Emotional readiness for RTP content (3 participants)	3
- Perception of completeness of the RTP	1
- Satisfaction with delivery format	1
- Perceived training efficacy despite condensation	1
- Confidence in outcome equivalence with condensed format (5 participants)	5
- Appreciation of coaching style	1
- Feeling validated and respect of participants' voices	1
- Clarity of instructions during the RTP workshops	1
- Positive perception of sessions sequencing during the RTP	1

- Appreciation of coherence and structure of the RTP (11 participants)	11
- Excitement during RTP sessions	1
- No issues to report (9 participants)	9
- Positivity of PPIs themselves helps overcome challenges faced during workshops	1
- Character strengths as key turning point (3 participants)	3
- Coaching supports understanding and simplification of PPIs (4 participants)	4
- Value of explanation and coaching style used (AC and ACR) (4 participants)	4
- Perceived difficulty of some PPIs resolved through facilitation (4 participants)	4
- Serious reflection in RTP	1
- User-friendly delivery	1
- Sign of ease of engagement with adapted PPIs	1
- PP tools retaining interest in participation (3 participants)	3
- Positive evaluation of structure and flow	1
- RTP's feedback loop	1
- Absence of difficulty (2 participants)	2
- RTP helps in self-awareness development	1
- Value of character strengths and strengths wheel effectiveness	1
- enhances commitment (2 participants)	2
- Accessibility of PPIs and PP concepts	1
- Perceived ease of activities	1
- Simplification of complex concepts	1
- Perceived usefulness of character strength activities (3 participants)	3
- Perceived usefulness of character strengths' identification	1
- Reflective journaling's benefits during RTP's workshops (6 participants)	6
- Universally beneficial PPIs in the RTP	1
- Usefulness of RTP (3 participants)	3
- Reduction in initial difficulty	1

- Progressive growth process during the RTP	1
- RTP helped in bridging emotional, cognitive, and developmental impact	1
- RTP facilitated dual guidance: positive and negative awareness	1
- Opinion about results of the training	1
- RTP supports reflection on life purpose and personal values	1
- Structure and successful delivery of the RTP	1
- Trustworthiness of the RTP process	1
- RTP that is trustworthy	1
- Ensured trust, authenticity, confidentiality and respect between others	1
- Feeling proud about personal outcomes of the RTP	1
- Trusting the training (RTP) process to change (4 participants)	4
- Enjoying RTP	1
- Joyful experience	1
- depth	1
- Emotional depth in peer coaching	1
- Values of the adapted and tailored PPIs to culture and context	1
- Simplicity of activity versus depth of impact	1
- Benefits of using pictures in self-compassion session	1
- RTP intriguing and fun experience as a whole (6 participants)	6
- RTP good impression from the outset	1
- Benefits of using pictures in self-compassion session	1
- Good training like it is (12 participants)	12
- Good organisation and structure of RTP	1
- Early gains in active learning from the very first workshop	1
- Sustained motivation	1
- Experience of ACR	1
- Creative and innovative design of RTP	1
- Enjoyable training (RTP) (3 participants)	3
- Originality of RTP	1
- RTP flow recognition (4 participants)	4

- I was thinking if we will really attain our goal at the end of the training	1
- Appreciation of the RTP (11 participants)	11
- Deep and fast positive impact of RTP (3 participants)	3
- Practical application of the RTP in real life situations	1
- Integrity of the groups	1
- RTP sustained motivation and engagement with PPIs (2 participants)	2
- Peer engagement	1
- Enjoyable surprise (3 participants)	3
- unlocked many things in myself,	1
- Positive emotional climate; Flow experience	1
- Psychological safety; Motivation to return (5 participants)	5
- Surprising engagement; Shift from boredom to motivation (2 participants)	2
- Emotional depth; Self-discovery; Gaining awareness; Reflective growth (9 participants)	9
- Comfort in applying RTP concepts learnt	1
- Relevance of RTP to personal and professional life	1
- Unexpected positive experience; Change in perception	1
- Positive surprises (2 participants)	2
- RTP helped in whole-person growth (2 participants)	2
- Sign of social diffusion of the RTP (2 participants)	2
- Satisfaction with current RTP structure	1
- Confirmation of method clarity and accessibility (10 participants)	10
- Ease of applying concepts (2 participants)	2
- Self-compassion session as a helpful and impactful PPI (10 participants)	10
- Visualisation technique as a helpful PPI (7 participants)	7
- Confidentiality of reflective journals during workshops (6 participants)	6
- Enjoyable learning experience (2 participants)	2
- Developing self-reflection skills (5 participants)	5

Table 5. Original codes under Subtheme -Negative evaluation of anything related to the RTP (for theme 2- Evaluation of the experience and future recommendation)

Codes under Subtheme-Negative evaluation of anything related to the RTP of theme 2- Evaluation of the experience and future recommendation	Coded segment
-Timing barriers to change	1
-Environmental setup interfered with reflective quality	1
-Difficulty in deeper reflective stages under poor conditions	1
-Noise preventing a greater involvement in the PPI	1
-Challenge of visualisation technique	1
-Challenge of self-compassion (2 participants)	2
-Stress-related timing constraints	1
-Interference with academic load	1
-Time pressure affecting reflective depth	1
-Condensation of RTP as a constraint on introspection (5 participants)	5
- RTP consuming effort and energy	1
-Environmental discomfort during Appreciative Inquiry	1
-Condensation of RTP as tiring and exhausting	1
-Signs of mental fatigue post sessions	1
-Reflective questions perceived difficult and challenging (2 participants)	2
-Peer coaching as new and difficult	1
-Emotional granularity wheel as unclear and difficult (2 participants)	2
-Difficulty in identifying top character strengths	1
-Co-coaching as challenging or novel (2 participants)	2
-Self-reflection as difficult	1
-Cognitive load (2 participants)	2
-Difficulty with vocabulary used in 3 life domains activity	1
-The strengths wheel activity perceived as least helpful	1
-Perceived normality of the visualisation technique due to familiarity with it (prior habits)	1
-Emotional granularity wheel perceived as least helpful (2 participants)	2
-Demanding self-reflection with 3 chosen life domains	1

-Emotional and cognitive difficulty of self-awareness (6 participants)	6
-Expectation of individual coaching format	1
-Misalignment of expectations; Desire for dynamic/physical learning	1
-Prior exposure	1
-I was faced with the challenge to choose only 5-character strengths from all the 24	1
-Challenge with drawing expressive activity (3 participants)	3
-Difficulty revisiting painful memories (2 participants)	2
-Emotional intensity of the intervention	1
-Lack of debriefing for symbolic activity (self-compassion pictures)	1
-Difficulty with the miracle question and visualisation technique	1
-Challenge of written reflection (2 participants)	2
-Challenge in prioritising character strengths (2 participants)	2
-Negative perception of traditional materials compared to PPIs	1
-Conceptual challenges with abstract/existential PP themes (2 participants)	2
-Repetition and discomfort with drawing in Appreciative Inquiry	1
-Perceived developmental limitation on purpose exploration	1

Table 6. Original codes under Subtheme-Recommend or not the training and why (for Theme 2-Evaluation of the experience and future recommendation)

Codes under Subtheme-Recommend or not the training and why of Theme 2-Evaluation of the experience and future recommendation	Coded segment
-Recommend the RTP (4 participants)	4
-Strongly recommend the RTP (6 participants)	6
-Already informal peer recommendation of RTP (2 participants)	2

Table 7. Merged code categories within Theme2- Evaluation of the experience.

Merged code category	n = Code category occurrences
Subtheme - Positive evaluation of aspect related to the RTP	

Overall positive evaluation of the RTP experience: Satisfaction, confidence and appreciation of the resilience training.	106
design encourages intrinsic motivation and engagement by improving relatedness, autonomy, and competence.	39
Reducing cognitive load, increasing perceived competence, clarity and simplified structure, altogether promote reliable implementation.	38
The experience's simplicity and relevance boost self-assurance and a pragmatic dedication to WB practices.	31
Coaching fosters relationships and security, improving participants' confidence and their willingness to make a meaningful commitment.	29
Reflection processes promote internal transformation, reassessment, and personal growth, demonstrating psychological significance and transferability.	28
The importance of strength-based interventions to facilitate positive identity, engagement and self-consistent motivation.	8
Challenges with Conceptual materials and abstract tools	23
Temporal and Cognitive Overload	14
Cognitive and emotional complexity of deep self-reflection	13
Misaligned delivery of the appreciative outdoor coaching environment and expectations	7
Disruption of introspective processes by the intervention environment	4
Emotional and cognitive resistance to self-confrontation	1
Preference for PPI delivery methods over conventional ones.	1
Subtheme - Recommendation or non-recommendation of the training	
Positive endorsement of RTP	12

Table 8. Original codes under theme 3-Impact on resilience and emotional regulation

Codes under theme 3 (i.e., Impact on resilience and emotional regulation)	Coded segment
-Anxiety management	1
-Anger and anxiety management	1
-Self-compassion	1
-Emotion regulation (4 participants)	4

-Emotional agility (3 participants)	3
-Uncertain about RTP's impact on the self	1
-Anger management	1
-Building protective factors	1
-Establishing self-boundaries	1
-Cognitive behavioural change through awareness (4 participants)	4
-Facing inner issues leading to intention to act	1
-From avoidance (contemplation) to self-awareness (preparation)	1
-New coping strategies with academic pressures (3 participants)	3
-Stress management improvement (3 participants)	3
-Problem solving (2 participants)	2
-Self-regulation and behavioural change (2 participants)	2
-Behavioural and cognitive change from the first workshops	1
-Progressive resilience development through cognitive simplification	1
-Reduction in initial difficulty-Better identification of emotions	1
-High demand for self-honesty	1
-Difficulty with emotional vulnerability	1
-Resistance to self-compassion	1
-Painful memory recall	1
-Recognition of cognitive challenges	1
-Naming strengths and weaknesses gained ability	1
-Emotional articulation for the first time	1
-Self-led cognitive behavioural change (repeated (15 times by the 12 participants in different segments)	15
-Self-reflection and self-awareness about cognitive behaviour (5participants)	5
-Coping through strength regulation	1
-Shift from avoidance to proactive coping	1
-From avoidance to action	1
-Memory recall via visualisation technique	1
-Recovery and grief	1

-Emotional awareness as a strength	1
RTP enables Emotional Agility (2 participants)	2
-Coping with past adversities	1
-Unprocessed trauma resurfacing	1
-Visualisation technique as a recovery tool	1
-Facing difficult memories	1
-Reduction of inner resistance (3 participants)	3
-Past situations resurfacing through visualisation	1
-Reconfiguration of issues (2 participants)	2
-Self compassion session beneficial	1
-Self compassion session beneficial	1
-Reconfiguring the challenges of everyday experiences	1
-Decision making under constraint	1
-Discovery of character strengths flexibility	1
-Emotional regulation literacy (2 participants)	2
-Strength's regulation (2 participants)	2
-Emotional literacy (2 participants)	2
-Emotional depth (3 participants)	3
-I unlocked many things in myself,	1
-self-awareness (3 participants)	3

Table 9. Merged code categories within Theme 3- Impact on resilience and ER.

Merged code category	n = Code category occurrences
Emergence of meta-emotional awareness and emotional Intelligence and regulation.	28
Improved coping skills, cognitive reframing, and functional adaption.	22
Emotional processing of vulnerability and pain through cognitive and emotional reprocessing, including acknowledgement of resistance and facilitating transformation.	22
Resilience building through behavioural and cognitive Shifts.	22
Psychological barriers and resistance	3

Table 10. Original codes under Theme 4- Impact on wellbeing and daily functioning

Codes under theme 4 (i.e., Impact on wellbeing and daily functioning)	Coded segment
-Life balance attainment / A sense of Life balance attainment (8 participants)	8
-Happiness (2 participants)	2
-Enhanced wellbeing (4 participants)	4
-Uncertain about RTP's impact on the self	1
-Energy protection	1
-Emotional self-regulation	1
-Finding one's own authenticity	1
-Emotional high during sessions	1
RTP promotes self-correction	1
-Skills acquisition and development	1
-Sign of personal agency (11 participants)	11
-Cathartic expression through confidential journaling	1
-Perceived well-being outcome (7 participants)	7
-Eudaimonic impact of RTP	1
-Purpose in life discovery	1
-Boost in self-confidence (4 participants)	4
-A deeper gain in eudaimonic wellbeing (5 participants)	5
-Simplifying learning boosted confidence	1
-Emotional insights from first workshops	1
-Application of gratitude through PPIs	1
-Cognitive emotional effort (2 participants)	2
-Emotional pain management	1
-Mindfulness and calm (8 participants)	8
-Feeling sense of safety and acceptance	1
-Expressive freedom (2 participants)	2

-Feeling validated and self-confidence (2 participants)	2
-Self-confidence (7 participants)	7
-Changing to flourishing behaviour (3 participants)	3
-Hope and future orientation (Flourishing) (10 participants)	10
-Emotional intelligence gain	1
-Emotional self-regulation gain (3 participants)	3
-Non-judgemental self-acceptance	1
-Self-reconciliation (3 participants)	3
-Self-worth (3 participants)	3
-Self-respect gain (2 participants)	2
-Balance achievement through strengths' activities	1
-Self-acceptance gain (3 participants)	3
-Cognitive and emotional clarity (2 participants)	2
-Mental clarity gain	1
-Positive thinking and optimism (5 participants)	5
-Self-awareness about purpose and meaning in life via the visualisation technique	1
-New exposure to profound self-reflection related to personal character strengths and self-acceptance (3 participants)	3
-Discovery of employing character strengths in reaching personal accomplishment (2 participants)	2
-Emotional catharsis and relief (4 participants)	4
-Self-discovery and Emotional release (2 participants)	2
-Flow state signs (2 participants)	2
-Emotional regulation (5 participants)	5
-Active enjoyment (2 participants)	2
-Impact on well-being	1

Table 11. Merged code categories within Theme 4- Impact on wellbeing and daily functioning.

Merged code category	n = Code category occurrences
Hedonic and eudaimonic wellbeing gains, positive affect, and hope.	43

Gains in self-confidence, self-worth, inner validation and self-acceptance.	28
Life balance, energy flow, and cognitive effort management.	20
Emotion Regulation and Insight Development.	18
Discovery of purpose and eudaimonic transformation.	17
Personal Agency and Positive Behavioural Integration.	15
Thoughtful hesitation or ambiguity in the perceived benefit.	1

Table 12 Original codes under Theme 5- Reflection and self-awareness

Codes under theme 5 (i.e., Reflection and self-awareness)	Coded segment
- Possible familiarity with reflection processes	1
- Self-acceptance as difficult to reflect on	1
- Self-awareness of Appreciative coaching guidance and ethics	1
- Reflective safety	1
- Self-awareness about unnoticed choices (6 participants)	6
- Self-knowledge	1
- Verbalising promotes awareness	1
- Challenge of self-awareness (6 participants)	6
- Self-awareness of internal emotional states (3 participants)	3
- Uncovering emotional blocks	1
- Structured reflection through first workshops	1
- Conceptual challenges with abstract/existential PP themes	1
- Self-awareness and self-reflection (2 participants)	2
- Deeper reflective content in RTP	1
- Challenging self-awareness and self-reflection (5 participants)	5
- Difficulty with emotional precision	1
- Embarrassment in recalling past endurance	1
- Difficulty of expression	1
- Self-reflection and self-awareness (2 participants)	2
- Challenge of the Appreciative Inquiry activity	1
- Challenge of choosing the top personal character strengths (2 participants)	2

- Self-reflection	1
- Self-awareness about personal achievements (2 participants)	2
- Trusting the process of PP and PPIs (2 participants)	2
- Personal outcomes from RTP in line with expectations	1
- Emotional self-awareness	1
- Discovering misapplication of personal strengths	1
- Deepened self-understanding (8 participants)	8
- Awareness of purpose and meaning in life	1
- Self-awareness about purpose and meaning in life via the visualisation technique	1
- Self-discovery (6 participants)	6
- Self-discovery and self-awareness via peer coaching and RTP	1
- Awareness about character strengths' importance (4 participants)	4
- Gained awareness about many things (2 participants)	2
- Deep self-reflection and self-awareness facilitated with the visualisation technique	1
- Self-awareness about unprocessed trauma resurfacing (3 participants)	3
- Deep self-awareness about the subconscious/ unconscious (8 participants)	8
- Tension in decision making	1
- Discovering personal prediction confirmation	1
- Validation of prior beliefs	1
- Enhanced reflection and self-awareness	1
- Difficulty of selection	1
- Awakening to personality traits	1
- Reflective tool	1
- RTP facilitating self-recognition and self-awareness (2 participants)	2
- Meaningful constraint	1
- Reflective difficulty	1
- Prior self-awareness baseline	1
- Self-discovery (3 participants)	3
- Prompting reflection	1
- Strength's flexibility awareness (3 participants)	3

- New self-assessment tool	1
- Reflective novelty	1
- Self-assessment (3 participants)	3
- Self-awareness (2 participants)	2
- unlocked many things in myself	1

Table 13. Merged code categories within Theme 5- Reflection and self-awareness.

Merged code category	n = Code category occurrences
Deep self-awareness and self-discovery	49
Activation of general self-reflection processes	22
Emotional resistance and challenges related to deep self-awareness.	19
Cognitive and existential challenges associated with reflective tasks.	16
Pre-existing self-awareness and intuitive continuity.	4

Table 14. Original codes under Theme 6- Recommendations for improvements

Codes under theme 6 (i.e., recommendations for improvements)	Coded segment
-Desire of earlier delivery of RTP as a preventive intervention (2 participants)	2
-Recommendation for reimagining the Appreciative Inquiry intervention (2 participants)	2
-Suggestion for changing drawing activity to card-based or discussion groups	1
-Suggestion for more outdoor activities outside the campus (3 participants)	3
-Suggestion to keep initial RTP timeline for the future	1
-Suggestion for better timing in academic year (3 participants)	3
-Needs for tutorials for independent use	1
- Suggestion for tech-enhanced visual expression (Artificial Intelligence or tablets) (3 participants)	3
-Suggestion for Artificial Intelligence enhanced tools in Appreciative Inquiry (3 participants)	3
-Suggestion for Tech-mediated visual expression (3 participants)	3

Table 15. Merged code categories within Theme 6- Recommendations for improvements.

Merged code category	n = Code category occurrences
Suggestions for methodological and pedagogical adaptation.	12
Recommendations for appropriate scheduling and early delivery of RTP as a preventive intervention for university freshmen.	6
Recommendation for environmental and contextual enrichment.	3
Support with tutorials for autonomous engagement	1

Table 16. Original codes under Theme 7-Positive education and whole person learning

Codes under theme7 (i.e., PosEd and whole person learning)	Coded segment
- Cognitive and social growth	1
- Theory-to-practice link of newly acquired skills	1
- Acquisition of in-depth knowledge of PP and the applicability of PPIs	1
- Sign of preparation stage (3 participants)	3
- Good timing as a mechanism for greater outcomes and transformation (3participants)	3
- Expression of felt emotional and psychological readiness for change (3participants)	3
- Relational active learning	1
- Well-structured pedagogical quality	1
- Understanding of the RTP flow (2 participants)	2
- Eased comprehension through trainer support (4 participants)	4
- Growth in empathy (2 participants)	2
- Social-emotional learning through peer coaching	1
- Transformative strategic thinking about goals and situations (4 participants)	4
- Empowerment in decision-making (6 participants)	6
- New insights and choices through reflection (2 participants)	2
- Sign of action stage (7 participants)	7
- Strategic regulation of strengths	1
- Life direction clarity gain (11 participants)	11
- Identity related insight	1

- Deep-level learning (2 participants)	2
- New coping strategies with academic pressure	1
- Peer coaching as Appreciative coaching and Active Constructive Respond (through cards)	1
- Understanding Appreciative Coaching	1
- Effective active learning method	1
- Transferability of learning from RTP to multiple life domains	1
- Practical personal and professional relevance of RTP	1
- Reflecting in one's life direction and meaning	1
- A deeper gain in eudaimonic wellbeing	1
- Self-knowledge for personal and professional use	1
- Character strengths as life relevant	1
- Active processing strategies during RTP (2 participants)	2
- Transferable life skills - active learning gains	1
- Problem identification via first PPIs	1
- Goal orientation guidance through first workshops (2 participants)	2
- Peer learning mechanism	1
- Social dimension of learning	1
- Practice-based learning	1
- Accessibility and inclusivity of strengths	1
- Card design enhanced learning	1
- Perceived ease of activities	1
- Increasing learning curve	1
- Progressive growth process during the RTP	1
- Strength's awareness (3 participants)	3
- Meaning and purpose in life	1
- Sustainable learning (SDG-linked, scalable) (2 participants)	2
- Workplace relevance	1
- Purpose-seeking	1
- Deep self-awareness about unconscious parts of the self	1

- Readiness and preparation for change	1
- Signs of integrity of the groups (all participants, we..) (2 participants)	2
- Commitment of the groups to appreciative coaching	1
- Peer-supported space as Appreciative Coaching and ACR's benefits	1
- Preparation to change	1
- Active learning gains around PP's subfields (2 participants)	2
- Interest in PP science (2 participants)	2
- Improving skills	1
- Future self	1
- Goal setting and motivation	1
- Personal behaviour awareness and taking action to change it (2 participants)	2
- Social skills development	1
- Social communication learning (2 participants)	2
- Guided personal growth via strength regulation	1
- Acquisition of Strengths regulation techniques (3 participants)	3
- Discovering unhelpful personal character strengths	1
- Personal values identification	1
- Identity formation	1
- Clarity of identity and values (3 participants)	3
- Insight from visualisation activity	1
- Practical application of the adapted PPIs in real life (2 participants)	2
- Whole person learning (3 participants)	3
- Value in experiential learning	1
- Growth and transformation with the RTP adapted and simplified PPIs (4 participants)	4
- Deep impact of adapted and tailored PPIs to culture and context on PosEd and growth mindset (3 participants)	3
- Novelty in learning method	1
- Growth mindset (10 participants)	10
- Shift in mindset toward growth (2 participants)	2
- Self-awareness (3 participants)	3

- Reflective problem solving (2 participants)	2
- Active Learning gain (10 participants)	10
- Active Learning gain (repeated 13 times by the participants)	13
- Experience of ACR	1
- Cognitive activation	1
- Discovery of character strengths flexibility	1
- Top character strengths' identification	1

Table 17 Merged code categories within Theme 7-Positive education and whole person learning.

Merged code category	n = Code category occurrences
Active and experiential learning strategies.	41
Readiness and action-oriented growth.	33
An ongoing, dynamic journey of learning and personal growth.	26
Development of character and identity.	18
Creation of meaning and goal-oriented learning.	18
Integration of knowledge and practices of PP.	16
Social and interpersonal learning gains.	15
Transferability and relevance of learning in life.	11